

SECTION OF BIOLOGICAL AND MEDICAL SCIENCES

SPLINTING TEETH IS ONE OF THE MANDATORY STAGES OF COMPLEX TREATMENT OF PERIODONTAL DISEASES

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Abstract

One of the leading symptoms of generalized forms of periodontal disease is pathological mobility of teeth. It is impossible to achieve remission of the pathological process without stabilizing mobile teeth. In order to preserve teeth and their function, various types of splinting are used. According to a number of authors, splinting ensures uniform distribution of the chewing load between the periodontal teeth, creates rest for the affected tissues, helps to increase the effectiveness of complex therapy and stimulates reparative changes in periodontal tissues.

Keywords: generalized periodontitis, tooth mobility, splinting.

Fixation of mobile teeth during periodontitis still remains an urgent problem due to changing age limits of patients with periodontal diseases and the widespread prevalence of aggressive forms of periodontitis [11]. Despite the variety of methods for splinting teeth for periodontitis, dentists daily face certain difficulties when trying to preserve teeth with mobility of III-IV degrees and, accordingly, improve the quality of life of patients with periodontitis [2]. It is known that periodontitis, being a multifactorial disease of periodontal tissues, not only causes discomfort to the patient in the form of bleeding gums, suppuration from periodontal pockets, pain and mobility of teeth, but also results in their loss, disrupting the aesthetics and physiology of the bite [8]. Dental immobilization is one of the most ancient procedures in the history of dentistry. Archaeological excavations have revealed that even the ancient Etruscan tribes in the 13th century BC used gold wire and rings for this purpose. In 1723, R. Fauchard wrote in his dental treatises about splinting procedures, when he used ligature binding of loose teeth for these purposes. Splinting techniques became widespread in the 20th century. For a long time, these were various ligation methods (silk braid, wire, fishing line, etc.). Subsequently, splinting techniques developed due to the advent of dental materials science [1]. Splinting of teeth is one of the mandatory stages of complex treatment of periodontal disease, as it allows to reduce the load on the periodontium and underlying tissues due to the redistribution of stress from an individual tooth to a group of teeth [10], eliminate traumatic articulation, reorient all occlusal forces along the long axis of the tooth, prevent migration and extrusion of teeth [7]. The splint provides rest to the affected tissues and increases the effectiveness of pathogenetically based and symptomatic therapy. Therefore, many authors believe that the best therapeutic effect of splinting is achieved in the

early stages of the disease, when the first signs of pathological tooth mobility appear [9]. The transmission of muscle forces to periodontal tissue occurs during chewing and swallowing, contacts of the dentition, in various phases of occlusion, and also indirectly through food, when there is a food bolus between the dentition. Under physiological conditions of an intact dentofacial system, the supporting apparatus of each tooth, when processing food, uses only part of its inherent ability to resist chewing pressure. The other part is its reserve, which is mobilized when a strong stimulus occurs and compensates for its pathological effect [2,3]. As atrophic processes develop, the functional capabilities of the periodontium decrease, and it is unable to respond with an adequate response to physiological stress. As a rule, it is believed that when the alveolar bone is atrophied at $\frac{3}{4}$ of the root length, the reserve capabilities of the periodontium are exhausted, and the tooth must be removed [6]. For choosing the design of a permanent splinting apparatus, what was put forward by V.Yu. Kurlyandsky's position on the reserve forces of the periodontium: "...The periodontium of an individual tooth has a reserve of reserve forces at least equal to the efforts expended to grind food under physiological conditions." It is safe to say that only the presence of physiological periodontal reserves allows the use of various designs of dentures. Classification of tires: - by duration: permanent, semi-permanent and temporary; - according to the method of fixation: removable and non-removable; - by manufacturing method: laboratory and clinical manufacturing; - by materials: metal, plastic, composite, combined; - according to the manufacturing method: cast, stamped, soldered, made by polymerization, ligature; - by design: using crowns, bridges, clasp and plate prostheses; - by location: supragingival and submucosal (root). Depending on their service life, tires are usually divided

into permanent (for years), semi-permanent (up to a year) and temporary. Temporary splinting (from 5-6 days to 2-3 months), used for the period of conservative and surgical procedures, after which inflammatory edema and an increase in pathological tooth mobility may occur, helps to reduce the negative impact on reparative processes in the periodontium [7]. Adhesive structures made from non-metallic reinforcement and light-curing composites are quite popular. Research by E.N. Zhuleva, E.E. Shchepetnoy [13] showed that splinting for moderate periodontitis helps restore physiological balance in the oral cavity, and temporary splinting with adhesive fiber splints in this regard is practically not inferior to permanent splinting. H.E. Bronnikov [6] believes that in patients with chronic generalized severe periodontitis, adhesive splinting should be used as a semi-permanent type of splinting, and the effectiveness and durability of such a splint directly depends on compliance with oral hygiene. N.I. Belikova [4] proposed a method of reinforcement-adhesive splinting with the placement of domestically produced fiberglass reinforcement material "Polyglass" on the vestibular surface of the front teeth, in which 6 months after the treatment, compared with the traditional oral placement of the splint, there are no complaints about the deterioration of the quality of the splinting structure and difficulties in oral hygiene, a slight deposition of dental plaque is determined in the absence of defects in the splinting structure. After 12 months, a decrease in the values of the OHI-S, IC and PMA indices was observed in comparison with the results obtained 6 months after treatment. Modern reinforcements used for splinting teeth are divided into two large groups according to their chemical composition: 1) materials based on an inorganic matrix – ceramic fibers and glass fibers ("Glass Span", "Splint-it", USA; "Fiber Splint", Switzerland); 2) materials based on an organic matrix – polyethylene fibers ("Ribbond", Ribbond Inc.), "Connect", Kerr, USA) [12]. Traditionally, the splinting technique is determined by the degree of tooth mobility during periodontitis. Classification of pathological tooth mobility according to E.E. Platonov (1951): I degree – mobility in relation to the crown of the adjacent tooth in the bucco-lingual (palatal) or vestibulo-oral direction by no more than 1 mm; II degree – mobility more than 1 mm in the same directions; mobility in the palatal-distal direction; III degree – the tooth is movable in all directions, including vertical, in the absence of neighboring teeth it can be tilted; IV degree of mobility (highlighted by D.A. Entin, 1953) – the addition of rotational movements of the tooth around its axis. Currently, solid metal structures, both removable and non-removable, are also used to fix mobile teeth during periodontitis. With a competent method of odontopreparation (with a ledge) and compliance with the requirements for all clinical and laboratory stages of manufacturing such prostheses, they do not exert significant pressure on the periodontium. Currently, the issue of tire stiffness is undergoing significant revision [5]. At the same time, the rigidity possessed by metal-ceramic dentures can aggravate the functional traumatic overload of not only the supporting teeth, but also their antagonists. Hard splints create

the highest stress levels, concentrated in the cervical area of the splinted teeth, and do not protect them from inclined loads. Therefore, a number of experts believe that periodontal pathology is a relative or even absolute contraindication to the use of metal-ceramic structures [8]. V.A. Based on the determination of mobility indicators and the resonance frequency of tooth vibrations obtained using a two-parameter periodontometer, Mironin concluded that teeth with relatively low mobility, not exceeding the norm by more than 1.5-3.0 times, can be used as a support for fixed teeth. Prostheses. Teeth, the supporting-retaining apparatus of which does not have physiological reserves, but mobility does not exceed the norm by more than 3.0-5.0 times, can be used as a support for removable dentures. For teeth with high mobility, exceeding the norm by 5.0-6.0 times or more, it is undesirable to make removable dentures with clasp fixation. There are also known methods for fixing mobile teeth with periodontitis of varying severity using aramid thread, both supragingival and submucosal [9]. These techniques relate to the rigid stabilization of splinted teeth and are usually extremely difficult to implement; they require circular preparation of grooves on the crowns of splinted teeth, which significantly damages the tissue, can contribute to the development of the carious process and reduce the existing gaps in the dentition, increasing crowding of the teeth. T.V. Melenberg [10] proposed a method for splinting the frontal group of teeth with pathological mobility of the III-IV degree and significant exposure of the roots during osteogingivoplasty (RF Patent for invention No. 2254097 dated June 20, 2005), which consists in the formation of two grooves in the area of the roots of the teeth row, placing an aramid thread in them and strengthening it with a composite material. However, root splinting with an aramid thread during osteoplasty excludes the natural micromobility of each splinted tooth and the entire splinted group of teeth, while the use of this technique with a thin type of mucous membrane (according to Supple) can lead to necrosis of soft tissues.

A review of the literature and analysis of various studies in the field of periodontology allows us to assert that splinting teeth has a positive effect in the treatment of periodontal tissue diseases. Reducing tooth mobility reduces or stops bone destruction. The chewing load is redistributed, which also helps reduce the load on the ligamentous apparatus of the tooth. The trophism of the periodontium improves, and the reparative processes in its tissues intensify. The requirements for modern tires are quite high. The splint should simply be placed and removed from the mouth. Adequately fixate. Do not cause additional trauma to the teeth being splinted. Allow teeth to remain in physiological mobility. The splint should not complicate oral hygiene and should be easy to clean. Do not damage gum tissue. Meet the aesthetic requirements of the patient. All these parameters required for dental splinting prove the need to develop an individual device to reduce tooth mobility and gives us the opportunity to assert that today there are no universal splinting structures that could be applicable in any clinical situation and satisfy all the requirements of

modern dentistry, those. To be effective and reliable without losing its aesthetics [4,5,9].

Conclusion.

Pathological tooth mobility is one of the leading symptoms of generalized forms of periodontal disease. A review of current literature and research in the field of periodontology allows the authors to state that the methods of temporary and permanent splinting are numerous. To date, there are no universal splinting structures that meet all requirements and are suitable for any clinical situation. The variety of clinical manifestations of pathology requires the development of new methods and materials.

References

1. Zhulev E.N., Shhepetnova E.E. Ortopedicheskoe lechenie hronicheskogo generalizovannogo parodontita kak jetap kompleksnogo jetiopatogeneticheskogo lechenija // Stomatologija «Obozrenie. Medtehnika». – 2-12. – №11 (75). – S. 34-36.
2. Zorina O.A., Berkutova I.S., Domashev D.I. i dr. Kachestvo zhizni pacientov s hronicheskim generalizovannym parodontitom tjazhelej stepeni i agresivnymi formami parodontita // Stomatologija dlja vseh. – 2012. – №3. – S. 12-15.
3. Parhamovich S.N. Primenenie adgezivnyh shin dlja stabilizacii podvizhnyh zubov pri kompleksnom lechenii zabojevanij periodonta // Sovrem. stomatol. – 2007. – №1. – S. 90-95.
4. Belikova N.I., Petrushanko T.A. Indeksnaia ocenka rezul'tatov shinirovaniia podvizhnyh zubov na osnove armaturno-adgezivnoj tehniki // Molodoj uchenyj. – 2013. – №7. – S. 114-118.
5. Parhamovich S.N. Primenenie adgezivnyh shin dlja stabilizacii podvizhnyh zubov pri kompleksnom lechenii zabojevanij periodonta // Sovrem. stomatol. – 2007. – №1. – S. 90-95.
6. Bronnikov O.N. Klinikofunkcional'naja sravnitel'naja ocenka metodov shinirovaniia u bol'nyh hronicheskim generalizovannym parodontitom: Avtoref. dis. ... kand. med. nauk. – M., 2005. – 23 s.
7. Guluev R.S. Ocenka jeffektivnosti primenenija adgezivnovolokonnyh materialov dlja vremennogo shinirovaniia v kompleksnom lechenii hronicheskikh parodontitov: Avtoref. dis. ... kand. med. nauk. – N. Novgorod, 2013. – 23 s.
8. Grudjanov A.I. Diagnostika v parodontologii. – M.: MIA, 2004. – 104 s.
9. Belousov H.H. Opredelenie jeffektivnosti shinirovaniia zubov pri tjazhelyh formah vospalitel'nyh zabojevanij parodontita // Parodontologija, 2009. – №3. – S. 41-44.
10. Zholudev S.E., Gol'dshtejn E.V., Shustov E.L. Izbirate'l'noe prishlifovyvanie i shinirovanie zubov kak zveno v kompleksnom lechenii parodontita // Institut stomatologii. – 2004. – №1. – S. 80-81.
11. Zholudev S.E., Delec A.V. Obosnovanie primenenija razlichnyh shinirujushchih konstrukcij pri atroficheskikh processah v tkanjah parodontita (obzor literatury) // Probl. stomatol. – 2013. – №4. – S. 16-22.
12. Zhulev E.N., Shhepetnova E.E. Ortopedicheskoe lechenie hronicheskogo generalizovannogo parodontita kak jetap kompleksnogo jetiopatogeneticheskogo lechenija // Stomatologija «Obozrenie. Medtehnika». – 2-12. – №11 (75). – S. 34-36.
13. Zorina O.A., Berkutova I.S., Domashev D.I. i dr. Kachestvo zhizni pacientov s hronicheskim generalizovannym parodontitom tjazhelej stepeni i agresivnymi formami parodontita // Stomatologija dlja vseh. – 2012. – №3. – S. 12-15.